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METHODS OF TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE TO FOREIGN STUDENTS

Abstract

The role of education at the present stage of Uzbekistan's development is determined by increased attention to the training of qualified specialists in any field of professional activity, increased attention to the humanization of society, the tasks of the state's transition to a democratic and legal society, implemented mainly by the most important factor in the humanization of socio-economic relations, the formation of new life attitudes of the individual - university. This article will discuss the relevance of which is the need for fundamental changes not only in the content of education, but also in the educational process itself, understood as a kind of combination of training foreign students (normatively consistent activity of society) and learning (individual significant activity of an individual subject, in which the experience of their life is realized).

Keywords: *quality, modernization, development personality-oriented learning, methods, techniques, abilities, inclinations, interests, value orientations.*

A developing society needs modernly educated, moral, enterprising people who can independently make responsible decisions in a choice situation, predicting their possible consequences, capable of cooperation, are distinguished by mobility, dynamism, constructiveness, and have a developed sense of responsibility for the fate of the country. At the present stage of society's development, the university faces the task of comprehensive development of the student's personality [1]. At the same time, education should ensure the spiritual and intellectual development of students. New types and kinds of educational institutions provide significant opportunities in the work of teachers. A modern university, where modern approaches to teaching are implemented, aims not only to teach students with different abilities, but also to develop a creative environment in lessons aimed at a personally oriented model of teaching, affirming the value of the student's personality. The principle of respect for the personality of the pupil and taking into account his spiritual potential in the

content of education is realized by introducing him to world culture, considered in the aspect of social experience. In this case, the essence of the educational process, i.e. the process of training, education and development, is the purposeful transformation of social experience into personal experience, introducing students to the entire wealth of human culture.

Currently, more and more leading teachers and psychologists adhere to this point of view. Among the large number of innovations used in the education system, special attention is paid to such technologies, where the teacher does not act as a source of educational information, but is the organizer and coordinator of the creative educational process, directs the students' activities in the right direction, while taking into account the individual abilities of each student. Among such technologies, the most famous is the technology of personality-oriented learning. This technology is one of the first in importance and the expectations associated with it for improving the quality of education [2].

Research in the field of technology of personality-oriented learning was carried out by such scientists as G.G. Kravtsova, T.A. Matis, Yu.A. Poluyanova, V.V. Rubtsova, G.A. Tsukerman, I.S. Yakimanskaya [3].

All researchers emphasize the need for an individual approach to teaching students, the importance of a unified educational strategy for universities as the main condition for successful work with students.

One of the main means of improving the quality of education in the context of modernization is the development of modern pedagogical technologies. The content of personality-oriented learning, methods, techniques are aimed at revealing and using the subject experience of each student, based on the identification of his individual abilities as a subject of knowledge and subject activity [4].

The educational process of personality-oriented learning provides each student, based on his abilities, inclinations, interests, value orientations and subject experience, the opportunity to realize himself in knowledge, educational activity, behavior. The content of education, its means and methods must be selected and organized so that the student can show selectivity to the subject material, its type and forms.

The criteria base of personality-oriented learning takes into account not only the level of achieved knowledge, skills and abilities, but also the formation of a certain intellect (its properties, qualities, nature of manifestations). Education as a set of knowledge, skills, individual abilities, is a means of developing spiritual and intellectual qualities.

In modern pedagogical science, the educational environment is becoming more humane, and there is a transition from an information model of learning to an activity-based and personal one. This model of learning requires new forms of organizing the educational process and pedagogical technologies.

In recent years, the educational space has been rapidly conquered by personality-oriented developmental learning. Developmental learning is that

which corresponds to the individuality of the student, his potential for acquiring knowledge. The popularity of the personality-oriented approach in learning is due to a number of objective circumstances [5]:

Firstly, the dynamic development of Russian society requires the formation of not so much the typical as the brightly individual in a person, allowing the student to become and remain himself in a rapidly changing society.

Secondly, modern students are pragmatic in their thoughts and actions, mobile and liberated, and this requires teachers to use new approaches and methods in interaction with students.

Thirdly, the modern university is in need of humanization of relations between students. The ideas and principles, psychological and pedagogical foundations of personality-oriented learning, the model of which was created by Doctor of Psychological Sciences I.S. Yakimanskaya, are the most attractive for solving the problems of developing the personality of the foreign student, revealing their individuality through learning. I.S. Yakimanskaya is a Doctor of Psychology, Professor, a full member of the International Pedagogical Academy and the New York Academy of Sciences, Head of the Department of "Designing Personality-Oriented Education in Secondary School" at the Institute of Pedagogical Innovations of the Russian Academy of Education.

According to the concept of personality-oriented learning, each student is an individual, an active subject of the educational space, with their own characteristics, values, attitude to the world around them, and subjective experience. In the context of a personality-oriented approach, each student appears to the teacher as a unique phenomenon. The teacher helps each student realize their potential, achieve their educational goals, and develop personal meanings of learning.

The model of personality-oriented learning meets the principles of conformity to nature, cultural conformity, individual-personal approach, and also implements the principles of humanitarian education, which promotes the development of imaginative perception and creative thinking, the formation of an emotional-personal attitude to learning.

The model of personality-oriented education is based on a scientific psychological and pedagogical concept, therefore, during its implementation, psychological and pedagogical support, participation, assistance and support of a psychologist are necessary. The interaction of a psychologist and a teacher in mastering the personality-oriented technology of teaching contributes to the implementation of one of the Priority Directions for the Development of Educational Systems of the Russian Federation - the introduction of new developmental technologies of teaching. The most important principles of a personality-oriented lesson:

Using the student's subjective experience

Updating existing experience and knowledge is an important condition that facilitates understanding and the introduction of new knowledge. Understanding in general is closely related to the personal experience of the subject and is carried out on the basis of past experience, knowledge, rules and other knowledge (about one's capabilities, factors of understanding, etc.). Understanding is the main component of the learning process. Variability of tasks, providing the foreign student with freedom of choice in their implementation and solving problems, using the most significant methods for him to work through the educational material.

Accumulation of knowledge, skills and abilities not as an end in itself (the final result), but an important means of realizing students' creativity.

Providing personally significant emotional contact between the teacher and foreign students in the lesson based on cooperation, co-creation, motivation to achieve success through the analysis of not only the result, but also the process of achieving it.

When implementing these principles, the information base of the lesson becomes truly developmental.

The main thing that a teacher works on in a personality-oriented educational space is the organization of an "event community" with the student, helping him to master the position of the subject of his own life activity. It is important that the student is able to overcome the passive position in the educational process and discover himself as a bearer of an active transformative principle.

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